

Shape Morphing for Data Augmentation : An Innovative Approach for Enhancing Insect Classification

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Abstract This work introduces an innovative intra-class morphing data augmentation method designed to improve insect classification in low-data scenarios. Leveraging As-Rigid-As-Possible (ARAP) deformation and landmark detection, the approach combines controlled geometric warping with realistic texture interpolation to generate synthetic images that remain faithful to species-specific morphological characteristics. The method was rigorously validated, both qualitatively and quantitatively, on the Leeds Butterfly Dataset and the Butterfly Moths Image Classification (100 Species) Dataset. When integrated into an InceptionV3 network pre-trained on ImageNet, the proposed augmentation leads to a significant improvement in classification performance, consistently outperforming traditional techniques such as Mixup, Cutout, and Rotation across key metrics, including precision, recall, accuracy, and F1-score.

Key words Data augmentation, Shape morphing, Landmark-based correspondence, Image generation, InceptionV3, Limited data learning.

1 Introduction

Agricultural pest management, particularly the control of *Ceratitis capitata* [1,2], represents a major challenge for global agriculture due to the significant economic losses these insects cause. While deep learning offers promising perspectives for their classification, its effectiveness is often limited by the lack of diverse annotated data, leading to a high risk of overfitting. Indeed, collecting such datasets in agricultural entomology is frequently costly, time-consuming, and sometimes unfeasible due to seasonal and biological constraints. In this context, data augmentation plays a crucial role : it enables the artificial generation of new samples from existing data while preserving their essential characteristics. This process enriches training sets, improves model generalization, and reduces the risk of overfitting [3].

However, classical data augmentation techniques such as geometric transformations (rotation, scaling, and flipping) [4-8] and photometric adjustments [9,10] provide only limited benefits for pest insect classification, as they fail to reproduce the natural intra-species morphological variations essential for reliable taxonomic identification.

More advanced generative approaches, including Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs : DCGAN, CycleGAN) [11] and Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) [12, 13], can produce realistic synthetic samples but frequently introduce visual artifacts or alter critical discriminative features, which may degrade performance on fine-grained tasks.

Recent studies have explored structural transformations and shape morphing for biological objects with high shape variability (Diffeomorphic transformations [14], faces [15], shapes via GFID [16]), demonstrating better preservation of topological and biological coherence compared to pixel-level or purely generative methods. Nevertheless, these approaches remain rarely applied to agricultural pest insects and still face limitations in terms of full automation or rigorous artifact filtering.

The present research overcomes these constraints by proposing an innovative intra-class data augmentation methodology based on As-Rigid-As-Possible (ARAP) [17] shape morphing, which identifies precise anatomical landmarks, applies local rigid deformation, and filters generated intermediates to preserve taxonomically relevant features while producing biologically plausible variations.

2 Methodology : ARAP-based shape morphing

Our approach exploits As-Rigid-As-Possible (ARAP) deformation [17], combined with landmark selection to progressively transform source images into target images while preserving their structural integrity. This strategy enables superior management of complex intra-class variations. Unlike classical augmentation methods, our approach explicitly models intra-class geometric variability, which is critical in fine-grained biological classification tasks. Figure 1 illustrates the overall workflow of the proposed method. Starting from an original dataset containing N images distributed across several classes, the pipeline proceeds as follows for each class : it extracts pairs of images belonging to the same class, applies ARAP-based morphing to generate intermediate images, filters out invalid or low-quality results, and then integrates the m validated images into the corresponding class. This results in an augmented dataset of $N + m$ images per class.

2.1 Core pipeline

The proposed data augmentation framework is based on a shape morphing strategy aimed at generating biologically plausible intra-class variations while preserving the structural integrity of insect specimens. The pipeline consists of several sequential stages, each ensuring geometric consistency and visual realism throughout the transformation process.

Stage 1 - Landmark identification : In the first stage, anatomical landmarks are defined using a semi-automatic strategy. An initial manual annotation is performed

FIGURE 1. ARAP-based Morphing Data Augmentation Pipeline from the original dataset, through landmark selection on insect pairs of the same class, generation of intermediate insects via ARAP morphing, cleaning of invalid images, to the final augmented dataset.

on the source image to ensure the biological relevance of the landmarks (antenna tips, wings, eyes, legs, head, and abdomen). An OpenCV-based interactive tool is then used to assist in matching these landmarks with the target image while maintaining user control. The points are stored following an identical indexing order in both images, ensuring a one-to-one and reproducible correspondence.

Stage 2 - Delaunay triangulation : A Delaunay triangulation is then constructed over the landmark sets of both images. The triangulation structure is kept identical for source and target images to ensure consistent correspondence between local regions. Image boundary corners are also included to guarantee full spatial coverage and to avoid boundary artifacts. This representation allows the global transformation to be decomposed into a set of local affine transformations.

Stage 3 - Affine transformation : For each triangle pair, an affine transformation A is decomposed via Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) into rotation R and scaling S components. The interpolated transformation is :

$$A(t) = R_t \cdot ((1 - t)I + tS), \quad t \in [0, 1] \quad (1)$$

where R denotes the rotation component, S the scaling component, and t controls the morphing progression while maintaining local rigidity.

Stage 4 - Image synthesis : Intermediate images are generated by applying interpolated triangular transformations to each region of the image and performing

photometric blending to ensure smooth visual transitions.

$$I_f(i, j) = I_s(i, j) \cdot \alpha + I_d(i, j) \cdot (1 - \alpha) \quad (2)$$

where I_s and I_d represent the source and target images, respectively, and $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ is linked to the interpolation parameter t .

This combination of geometric warping and intensity blending enables the generation of realistic and coherent intermediate samples. Figure 2 illustrates a typical morphing sequence generated by the proposed ARAP-based pipeline, demonstrating progressive and realistic intermediate images from source to target.

FIGURE 2. Sequence of intermediate images generated through our shape morphing process, showing a smooth transition between source and target insect images.

Stage 5 - Post-processing and Filtering : A post-processing module is applied to remove low-quality samples. Images exhibiting blur, artifacts, or geometric inconsistencies are filtered using sharpness metrics (e.g., Laplacian variance) and structural consistency criteria. This step ensures that only high-quality and reliable samples are retained for model training.

2.2 Key advantages

The ARAP-based approach offers distinct benefits over traditional methods : (1) preservation of taxonomic features essential for species identification, (2) controlled introduction of realistic intra-class variations, (3) maintenance of topological consistency throughout transformation, and (4) generation of biologically plausible intermediate samples without the artifacts commonly produced by generative models.

3 Dataset and Experimental Setup

3.1 Dataset

In this study, two small public datasets were employed due to the lack of corpora specifically dedicated to agricultural pests. The first dataset is the Leeds Butterfly Dataset [18], which includes 408 high-resolution images distributed across 10 classes (30 to 82 images per class). It was selected for its visual quality, the availability of annotations, and the significant intra-class morphological variability it provides. The second dataset is a subset of the Butterfly & Moths Image Classification Dataset [19],

composed of 15 distinct classes of butterflies or moths, each containing 15 to 20 images. Although these datasets do not directly target agricultural pests, the lepidopterans they include exhibit anatomical structures similar to those of many harmful insects. This morphological resemblance helps compensate for the absence of pest-specific data and paves the way for transferability to more applied datasets.

3.2 Implementation Details

We employed the InceptionV3 model pre-trained on ImageNet [20], adapted for a 10-class classification task. Training was carried out using the Adam optimizer with an initial learning rate of 0.001, on normalized images of 299×299 pixels, with the dataset split into 70% training, 10% validation, and 20% testing. An ARAP morphing augmentation layer was integrated in real time to generate intra-class intermediate samples during training. In addition, a progressive fine-tuning protocol was applied to optimize transfer learning. The experimental study was conducted using Python and the Keras framework.

3.3 Qualitative Results

We present here qualitative results of data augmentation using ARAP morphing applied to the different datasets. Figures 3 and 4 illustrate several examples generated from the Butterfly Dataset and the Leeds Butterfly & Moths Image Classification Dataset, respectively.

The analysis shows that the generated samples faithfully preserve essential morphological characteristics such as wing structures, patterns, and colors while introducing notable intra-class variability. This approach produces realistic and semantically coherent intermediate specimens, effectively addressing the structural gaps of the original dataset. These results confirm that the proposed augmentation technique consistently enriches the corpus and strengthens the robustness of the classification model. In all cases, the observations are visually satisfactory. Nevertheless, validating this impact requires a rigorous quantitative evaluation, which is presented in the following section.

3.4 Quantitative results and comparison with classical techniques

Classification Performance :

By comparing the Morphing-ARAP-InceptionV3 model with the standard InceptionV3, we demonstrated that integrating ARAP-based intra-class morphing augmentation into the architecture yields significant improvements in loss and accuracy across both datasets. On the **Leeds Butterfly Dataset**, the baseline model trained without augmentation achieved an accuracy of 95.18% with a loss of 13.57, as reported in Table 1. After incorporating the proposed morphing strategy, classification accuracy increased to 99.26%, corresponding to an absolute gain of 4.08%.

FIGURE 3. Examples of images generated through ARAP morphing data augmentation applied to the Leeds Butterfly Dataset [18].

FIGURE 4. Examples of images generated through ARAP morphing data augmentation applied to the Butterfly & Moths Image Classification Dataset [19].

Simultaneously, the loss decreased substantially to 2.50, indicating improved optimization stability and enhanced generalization capability. Similarly, on the **Butterfly & Moths Image Classification Dataset**, the baseline model reached an accuracy of 85.70% with a loss of 25.37. With the ARAP morphing augmentation, accuracy increased to 97.11%, corresponding to a gain of 11.41%, and the loss decreased to 6.25 as shown in Table 2. These findings confirm the effectiveness of the proposed method in strengthening both training stability and generalization capability for classification tasks.

Comparison with Conventional Augmentation Techniques :

To further validate the effectiveness of the proposed approach (ARAP-M), we compared it against widely used augmentation techniques, including Mixup [21–27], Cutout [28], and rotation-based augmentation [4–8]. The comparative results are presented in Tables 1 and 2, where the morphing-based strategy consistently achieves the highest performance across all evaluation metrics. In particular, it reaches **99.26%** accuracy, **99.20%** precision, **99.40%** recall, and **99.00%** F1-score on the *Leeds Butterfly Dataset*, while also attaining **97.76%** accuracy, **96.85%** precision, **97.40%** recall, and **97.04%** F1-score on the *Butterfly & Moths Dataset*. These findings indicate that geometry-aware augmentation better preserves discriminative morphological features than pixel-level or stochastic transformations.

TABLE 1. Comparison of augmentation strategies using InceptionV3 trained on the Leeds Butterfly Dataset [18] according to various performance metrics .

Method	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-score (%)	Loss (%)
Without augmentation	95.18	93.50	93.30	93.20	13.57
Mixup [21–27]	98.70	98.80	98.10	98.40	3.77
Cutout [28]	98.17	97.90	97.50	97.90	8.42
Rotation [4–8]	99.08	98.80	98.80	98.80	3.24
Ours(ARAP-M)	99.26	99.20	99.40	99.00	2.50

The analysis of the training curves (Figure 5) highlights the effectiveness of learning discriminant patterns through morphing. While the model without augmentation exhibits the lowest performance, methods such as Mixup and Cutout provide gradual improvements but remain below the performance of the rotation technique. However, the morphing-shape approach (ARAP-M) stands out by consistently achieving the highest training accuracy and the lowest loss. These superior learning dynamics validate the method’s capability to generate high-quality synthetic data for insect identification in contexts of limited datasets.

TABLE 2. Comparison of augmentation strategies using InceptionV3 trained on the Butterfly & Moths Image Classification 100 species Dataset [19] according to various performance metrics .

Method	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-score (%)	Loss (%)
Without augmentation	85.70	83,10	82,60	83,20	25.37
Mixup [21–27]	92.70	92.80	91.80	92.30	12.68
Cutout [28]	91.57	90.90	89.70	90.86	15.4+3
Rotation [4–8]	93.13	93.50	93.20	92.80	8.02
Ours(ARAP-M)	97.76	96.85	97.40	97.04	6.25

FIGURE 5. Comparison of training accuracy (a) and loss (b) using InceptionV3 trained on the Leeds Butterfly Dataset.

4 Conclusion

This study introduces a shape morphing-based data augmentation strategy that significantly enhances insect classification performance in limited-data contexts. By integrating ARAP deformation with landmark-based correspondence, the methodology generates synthetic images that preserve taxonomic integrity while introducing controlled morphological variations. Experimental validation on both the Leeds Butterfly Dataset and the Butterfly & Moths Dataset confirms the effectiveness of the proposed approach, achieving 99.26% accuracy with the InceptionV3 architecture on the former and 97.76% accuracy on the latter, consistently outperforming classical augmentation methods such as Mixup, Cutout, and Rotation.

The proposed approach provides a scalable and ecologically relevant solution for agricultural pest monitoring and biodiversity conservation. Future research will adapt the method to *Ceratitidis* fruit fly classification by building a dedicated dataset and analyzing morphological variations across pest species. It will also explore combining ARAP-based morphing with other augmentation techniques to improve robustness, and automate landmark selection using machine learning. Further improvements will include more complex morphing transformations, hybrid approaches with deep learning, and extension to 3D data, with validation on real agricultural pest datasets to assess practical applicability.

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